

THE ROLE OF RUSSIAN SCIENTISTS IN THE STUDY OF THE COUNTRY OF TURKEYSTAN

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ANNOTATION: Russian scientists the historical monuments of Uzbekistan and Turkestan in general have attracted the attention of many Russian scientists. Russian local historians P.I. Lerkh, N.I. Veselovsky, V.A. Zhukovsky, V.V. Bartold, M.S. Andreev, V.L. Vyatkin, A.L. Kuhn, A. The work of A. Semyonov, N. P. Milonov and M. V. Lomonosov is incomparable. During the registration of historical monuments and conducting research in them, the Russian Archaeological Society considered the historical, archaeological, linguistic and ethnographic study of Central and East Asia..

KEY WORDS: Society, committee, circle, archeology, ethnology, country, tsarism, tribute, tax, topography, map.

INTRODUCTION

There is a historical development of the peoples of the world, which has been going on for several hundred thousand years. But for several thousand years of this long historical development, written works have appeared, and before that there was no history in the Peoples, which was finished by writing. However, many of the events remained largely undeciphered after the introduction of the inscription. Moreover, the orders of the Kings, the religious teachings of the priests, the calculations of the treasures, written works about various wars and could not adequately reflect the domestic life of the people. Research on this has highlighted the role of the Great Silk Road as well. In the study of our country and the development of tourism here, it closely connects Central Asia with Europe and the East.

The science of historical local lore was conducted and founded on the basis of scientific and methodological and pedagogical experiments created by Russian historical scientists. In particular, the famous Russian historian local history scientist N.P.Milonov wrote that in 1761 M.V.Lomonosov's questionnaire on the research of the history of the country with the participation of local residents and young people mentioned that it served as a program of historical local lore in Russia. In the study of the territory, by 1788, the government was required to provide information on the history and people of the ancient gubernas, how historical memorial objects reflecting the life of the people who lived there were preserved mounds, farming, livestock, fishing, crafts, newly created factories, factories and trade works were established, where the developed products were allocated for sale, While the science of local lore was founded in Russia, scientific research by scientists indicates that the question of the study of the land began a long time earlier than in Russia on the territory of Central Asia, including Uzbekistan. Russian scientists carried out several scientific tadiiotic works on the study of this territory long before the conquest of Central Asia by chorism. However, in the first half of the 19th century, the study of the land, that is, local historiography, was suitable for the biquality of socio-political, economic and cultural life, and served mainly in the interests of rulers. History has been used to ideologically justify the interests of large landowners, the Khans, and the succession to the throne of their dynasty. Court historians have focused on describing political realities - the activities of the Khans, praising their victories over their opponents by raising them to the blue, and the traditions at court. Even in such complex and difficult conditions, the local residents tried to freely state their opinions and opinions.

After the conquest of Central Asia by Tsarist soldiers in the second half of the XIX century, Russian scientists here conduct a lot of scientific research. Russian scholars who came to Central Asia were closely associated with the progressive local intelligentsia in the region. The difficulties of the affairs of the colonial administration cause Central Asia not to be well studied. The natural resources and cultural heritage of the country were of interest to Russian scientists.

Russian zoologist and zoogeographer N.A.Seversov studies the physical and geographical aspect of most of Turkestan and the orography of the Pamir Ridge Mountains. N.A.In the course of his scientific research, Seversov collects very valuable collections on zoology, botany, mineralogy and paleontology. In addition, the Russian geographer I.P.Semyonov-Tyanshansky explored the Tyanshan Ridge Mountains of Central Asia, the Russian naturalist and traveler A.P.Fedchenko explores the Fergana Valley, the Oloy, the

Zarafshan Valley and the Kyzylkum.

Geologist and geographer I.V.Mushketov, on the other hand, showed the geological basis of the orography of the North Tyanshan Ridge Mountain. He described most of the mineral deposits in Turkestan and compiled an early record of Turkestan minerals. I.V.Mushketov travels to Oloy, Pamir, Bukhara, Hisor, amudarya and Kizilkum in 1877-1879 with the aim of carrying out geological inspection work. In 1881, g.D.Together with Romanovsky, he draws up the first geology map of Turkestan. I.V.Mushketov covered scientific research and the scientific work of other scientists who studied Turkestan in his monograph "definition of Geology and orography of Turkestan" and in his book "history of the study of Central Asia".

Russian scientist V.V.Dokuchaev also laid the foundation for modern scientific Soil Science, and in 1898 V.V.Dokuchaev provides early valuable information in the field of local lore in most of his works.

It was not until 1967 that the topography of Turkestan was studied. Only on the shores of the Caspian and Aral Sea, the foothills of Syrdarya and Amudarya, the shores of Lake Balkhash and some other places have been studied, except. Military topographers have done extensive surveying work for a large area.

After the conquest of Turkestan, the goal of mapping the territory and creating a scientific base on military topographers to study its climate is born, and statistical committees played an important role in the study of the territory during this period. The Turkestan Statistical Committee of 1868 was formed, on the initiative of which the publication of the collection "materials for the statistics of the Turkestan territory" was established from 1872. Later, from 1887, statistical committees were formed in Syrdarya, Tashkent, Samarkand, Fergana and Marghilan regions. The collection provided data on natural and manufacturing, national economy, irrigation systems, roads, population and its occupation, tribute and taxes, administrative structure, health, education, public improvement and weather observations.

In 1872, Orientalist A.L.Kun composed the "Turkestan album" (photocopied on ethnography, archaeology, occupation and history of Turkestan). This rare work has not lost its scientific value to this day. By 1917, the Turkestan branch of the Russian Geographical Society operated the regional magazines "Turkestan agriculture" and "Turkestan peasant".

The historical monuments of Uzbekistan and Turkestan as a whole have attracted the attention of many Russian scientists. In the 19th century, osori carried out archaeological research on atica. In this regard, the Russian local Turkestan scientists P.I.Lerx, N.I.Veselovsky, V.A.Zhukovsky, V.V.Bartold, M.S.Andreev, V.L.Vyatkin, A.L.Day and A.A.The work of the Semyonov was incomparable. In the accounting and scientific study of historical monuments of the former Turkestan, one of the scientific institutions in the center, the Imperial archaeological Commission, the Eastern branch of the Russian Archaeological Society, also focused on the committee for the study of Central and east Asia in historical, archaeological, linguistic and ethnographic terms.

Russian amateur collectors I.F.Barshchevsky, V.L.Vyatkin, V.A.Dobromyslov, A.D.Kastalsky, V.L.Komarov, Petrov-Borzna, B.D.Poslavsky, A.S.Stolyarov, A.A.Terentev and J.A.Trofimov collected valuable information. From the most important sources of Central Asian history as a result of archaeological research, Muhammad Narshahi's 10th-century "history of Bukhara" was published in 1897 by the scholar N.S.Likoshin was translated into Russian, and V.V.Bartold published under Edit. Currently, in 1871-1889, finds from archaeological objects are kept in museums opened in Tashkent, Samarkand and Fergana.

In 1895, the Russian archaeologist N.I.Under the direction of veselovsky, the architect A.V.With the participation of Shchusev and other specialists, the Imperial archaeological Commission organizes a scientific trip with the aim of studying the architecture and architectural decoration of the monument to Gouri Amir in Samarkand. The results of the research work on this scientific trip are out of print in the form of an album in 1905.

Russian Orientalist scientists in the study of the territory V.V.Bartold, N.I.Veselovsky, V.V.Radlov and A.N.The works of the samoylovichs are significant from the point of view of ethnography, at which time, along with Orientalists, doctors were involved in ethnographic research of the Uzbek population. Along with ethnographic observations, the collection of collections from the living and household items of the Uzbek people, clothing, ornaments, weapons, household items and production weapons was also carried out. A. in the field of study of the national economy.F.Middendorf's work," the Fergana Valley", has not lost its value today. Scientists have also focused on studying the composition of the population of Uzbekistan. In this regard, Russian scientists A.I.Pashino, P.S.Nazarov and I.I.The Krauze publish works devoted to the study of their professional work.

In the late 19th and early 20th centuries, middle Asian carpets were interested in Russian and European countries. In 1908-1909, a.A.Bogolyubov's album, which collects information about various

carpet copies, including Turkmen carpets, partly Uzbek carpets, is out of print. A.A. For the first time in this album, Bogolyubov classifies carpets on a scientific basis. A.A. After Bogolyubov's album art collector A. Falkerzam and S.M. Dudin's books describing Central Asian carpets are published. In this period, as in each period, in the study of the territory, scientists put in front of them anew-a diary of new requirements and tasks. It has done a lot of money to solve the requirements and tasks. However, there were practically no state research institutions in the territory. This situation encourages the formation of a scientific society in the territory with the support of major scientists in Moscow and Petersburg. The formation of scientific societies required the need to coordinate the scientific work of local Turkestan scientists. Thus, the scientific societies of Turkestan take a solid place in the history of the study of the territory.

In 1870, the Society of scholars of Central Asia was founded, which aims to promote and promote information on the history, geography, ethnography, statistics, economy of Central Asia. This society holds its first open meeting in 1871 and is named after the Russian geographer A.P. With the active participation of Fedchenko, the Turkestan Department of the Society of amateurs of Natural Sciences, archeology, anthropology and Ethnography opens. In 1878, V.F. As a result of a scientific trip organized under the leadership of Oshanin, Peter The Great led the mountains of the ridge, the Mugsuv River Glacier, to which A.P. Fedchenko is named after. Due to lack of funds, the department experienced considerable hardship and was forced to cease its operations in about 1893. The Division Has A.P. In addition to Fedchenko, members of the department include geologists and geographers N.A. Seversov, I.V. Musketov and V.F. There have been Russian scholars such as Oshanin. The division published its first and final work, "Memoirs of the Turkestan section of the Society of amateurs of natural science, archaeology, anthropology and Ethnography", in 1879. In this collection, N.A. Data from the Pamir vertebrate fauna of Seversov, N.B. Scientific papers have been collected on Teix's definition of the climate of the country. In 1895, amateur archaeologists laid the foundation for the Turkestan archaeological amateur circle, and the members of this circle found and studied the carved figures of Soymaylitosh in the Fergana mountain ranges, the opening of the famous Biya-Nayman ossuaries of the Chronicle of science were scientific discoveries.

In archaeology, as in other fields of Archaeology, research work was not organized in a planned manner, for which reason it was not possible to carry out scientific research due to the lack of specialists. During this period, archaeological research studies mainly relied on sources of writing to study historical monuments, examining and identifying some archaeological sites. Archaeological research work is rarely organized. The issues and considerations that the members of the circle shared, although unable to withstand the test of the times, were of great importance to this period. Their work was the impetus for the development of research thought, and they attracted the attention of the entire scientific community. Russian Orientalist V.V. Bartold was a major contributor to the work of the circle. A group of local scientists V.F. Ashanin et al. On the initiative of the Zhilinskys, the Turkestan Department of the Russian Geographical Society of 1897 is organized. This scientific section studies the Aral Sea, Lake Balkhash, Turkestan glaciers and fauna. About 15 scientific societies were working in the country, which left their mark on science. They have done research in geology, geography, zoology, botany, economics, agriculture, industry, history, Oriental Studies, archaeology, ethnography, anthropology, medicine and Sciences.

Orientalist A.L. On the day's scientific journey to Iskandarkol, Mirzo left a diary of Abdullo Abdurahman in which letters on ancient stones and tombstones were recorded. At this time, the Bukharan historian Muhammad Vafa was known for his collection of ancient carpets, manuscripts, and rare pottery. Of the amateur geographers, Olimhoja Yunusov, Mirza Hakim and others worked as employees of the Turkestan section of the Russian Geographical Society.

Scientific societies in Turkestan continued to exist in the early 20th century. The Turkestan Department of the Russian Geographical Society has done a great job of studying the country in a natural-historical way, introducing its flora and fauna, climate. Among the work carried out by the Department of society is L.S. Berg's research takes place. L.S. Bergning surveys Lake Balkhash with the Aral Sea, the largest body of water in Central Asia, in 1899-1903. L.S. Berg's monograph, "the Aral Sea", describes the results of the island's cross-sectional study. L.S. Berg's work provides rich historical accounts of changes in the water regime and changing sea levels, and of the inhabitants of amudaryo, Oryolbuyi Coast.

The Department of society is a Soviet and Russian writer in the field of study of Turkestan glaciers g.B. Leonov Talas Olatovi, N.L. Korzhenevsky Seldara and Karasel (the first was named Fedchenko, the second was named Mushketov) and V.G. Gorodesky Zaili studies the olatov glaciers. V.F. Oshanin, on the other hand, introduced the land fauna, N.A. Zarudny Turkestan poultry, B.A. Fedchenko and his mother o.A. Fedchenko described the plant world of the country, B. Ya. Korolenko, G.B. Leonov studied earthquakes

in Turkestan. As a result of these works, the society Department publishes data describing 80 different new seeds, species and subspecies of flora and fauna.

In 1907, the bibliographer I.V.Under Dmitrovsky's leadership, work on the composition of the "Turkestan collection" began anew. Until 1917, the number of volumes of the collection was increased to 394 (now it is stored in the Alisher Navoi State people's library of Uzbekistan). The collection contains extensive information on the history, archaeology, ethnography, literature, economics, history of culture and other issues of Central Asia and its neighboring Eastern countries.

The history and archaeology of Central Asia begins to be studied more deeply from the beginning of the 20th century. Orientalist academic V.V.Bartold's mastery of Oriental Languages was not always at the center of his scholarship, but at the same time had the opportunity to thoroughly study the sources of the history of the entire "Muslim East". V.V.Bartold's "Turkestan in the age of the Mongol invasion", which covers the years 1898-1900, made a significant contribution to science in the study of the past of Central Asia in terms of its richness in information. V.V.Bartold's "Ulughbek and his time", "on the irrigation history of Turkestan" are highly valuable and unimportant works. Event on the field of study of the history and archeology of Central Asia V.V.Bartold was not without his participation.

Colonel A.G.Serebrennikov collected interesting sources in the study of the history of Central Asia from 1839 to 1876. These were data collected using the archives of Petersburg, Moscow, Orenburg, Tiflis and Omsk. Only 14 volumes have been published from this information. During this period, local archaeologists were told that V.L.Vyatkin's scientific research work has been notable. V.L.Vyatkin studied the remains of the famous Ulughbek Observatory in Samarkand in 1908 by opening it. He was engaged in the study and preservation of Samarkand monuments and carried out scientific research work around the ancient afrosib fortress. V.V.With Bartold's proposal, the Turkestan archaeological amateur circle was established in October 1895. In the circle, he took on such tasks as studying ancient monuments in the Turkestan region, describing them, preserving archaeological monuments, conducting excavations of archaeological monuments on the basis of permission. The circle of archaeologists from this period was headed by the Governor-General of Turkestan, baron B.A.Vrevsky served as chairman. Tougarakga V.V.Bartold, D.M.Levshin, N.S.Likoshin, K.V.Aristov and V.F.Made up of scientists such as the oshanins. The circle was strongly influenced by Russian intellectuals in a progressive mood, and paid tribute to Central Asian history and ancient monuments, and was passionate about scientific research.

In conclusion, even if historical works created by local historians have not been able to reveal the socio-economic roots of the country's economy, economic relations, class struggle, popular movements and political events, students can use a critical point of view in the study of the country, in the compilation of Chronicles, in the discovery of ethnographic materials and toponymic data. These works are therefore very relevant in the study of the history of the territory before 1917. Because their authors lived at that time, saw with their own eyes the events and phenomena that occurred, and also compared them with the events of the previous period.

REFERECES:

- [1] Б.В.Лунин. Научные общества Туркестана и их прогрессивная деятельность. Ташкент, Изд-во «Наука», 1962.
- [2] Я.Х.Ғаффоров. Тарих ўқитиш методикаси. Дарслик. Ташкент, Ишончли ҳамкор. 2021. 276 б.
- [3] М.Лафасов, М.Хўжамов. Тарихий ўлкашунослик ва туризм. Ташкент, 2007. 108 б.
- [4] А.Набиев. Тарихий ўлкашунослик. Тошкент, Ўқитувчи. 1996. 40 б.
- [5] А.Асқаров. Ўзбекистон тарихи. Тошкент, Ўқитувчи. 1994.
- [6] А.Набиев, О.Бўриев, И.Шоймардонов. Ўзбекистон тарихини ўқитишда этнографик материаллардан фойдаланиш. Тошкент, Ўқитувчи. 1996.
- [7] Жабборов Исо. Ўзбек халқи этнографияси. Тошкент, Ўқитувчи. 1994.